

DERDE INTERNATIONAAL ACCOUNTANTS-CONGRES TE NEW-YORK IN SEPTEMBER 1929

Wij drukken hieronder af het „Tentative Program” van het boven-
genoemde congres, dat in het Engelsch heet: „Third International
Congress on Accounting”.

Note:

The leading papers are to be printed and distributed to all delegates
and members at the opening of the Congress in French, German and
English. An edition will be printed in Spanish if sufficient interest is
elicited.

It is not intended that the printed papers shall be read. It is assumed
that the delegates will have read and digested them in advance.
Hence the Chairman of each meeting will merely present the authors
whereupon the subject will be open for discussion from the floor.
This will afford more time for the delegates to discuss the papers. Five
minutes at the closing will be allowed for the author of a paper
to reply if he desires to avail himself of the opportunity.

Those who desire to discuss papers should register their wishes with
the Secretary in advance of each meeting. The time allotted to each
speaker will depend upon the number who register.

First Day MONDAY September 9, 1929

10.00 a.m. to 12.30 p.m.

Topic: Legislation.

Prepared papers on Legislation relating to Accounting throughout
the world since the last congress in Amsterdam, Scotland, England,
Holland, France, Germany, Italy, Czecho-Slovakia, Spain, Ireland,
United States, Canada, Asia (Japan), Australia, South Africa, South
America. Other countries, if delegates are sent therefrom.

Discussion:

General summary of papers, by a delegate from the United States.
General discussion from the floor.

Among the topics which may come up in any discussion under
this heading we may mention.

Legislation affecting the public practice of accounting.

Legislation which may affect accounting in the determination of
costs for import duties, etc.

Legislation affecting accounting in private industry for tax purposes,
or in mergers or cartels.

Legislation affecting public and private accountants in so far as it
concerns their responsibilities to creditors and investors; more par-
ticularly, in view of wider distribution of shares and bonds what has
been or what may be done to safeguard the interests of internal and
external investors.

Legislation affecting the accountant in his relation to Management

Legislation affecting the accountant in prospectuses.

12.30 p.m. to 2.00 p.m. Luncheon

2.00 p.m. to 4.30 p.m.

Topic: Education

Papers relating to Educational activities of professional and private
associations; such as

National association of Cost Accountants (U.S.A.)

Cost works accountants of other nations

National Electric light Association

Controllers Associations

Trade Associations (such as newsprint paper association and
others)

Professional societies

The purpose here being to secure all available data as to organized
educational work in accounting conducted by private and professional
bodies.

Papers relating to Educational programs of public accountants
conducted by their own staffs; the character, scope and results
obtained.

Papers relating to Educational Programs in accounting in Univer-
sities throughout the world.

Note:

During the sessions of the Congress, an exhibit will be held in the
buildings of New York University at Washington Square of all the
uniform cost systems of trade associations and industries. Efforts will
be made to have representatives of these associations present at stated
hours for the purpose of explaining the systems to the delegates.

During the sessions of the Congress an exhibit will be held in the
building of School of Business of Columbia University of historical

material relating to accounting from the earliest times down to recent
dates. Photostatic material and actual books and documents will be
on display. It is hoped that other Institutions and organizations will
cooperate in loaning material.

If the discussion of the foregoing topics is not completed on Monday
arrangements will be made to organize luncheon groups on Tuesday
under definite leadership to continue the discussion at luncheon.

Second Day TUESDAY September 10, 1929

10.00 a.m. to 12.30 p.m.

Topic: Depreciation

Papers on theories of Depreciation, viz; retirement reserve theory
(as adopted by the public utilities); annuity theory (Mr. G. O. May
suggested); straight line depreciation.

Papers or Problems of Depreciation and obsolescence.

a. from the standpoint of taxation

b. from the standpoint of the investor in securities

c. as affected by re-appraisals

d. as affected by progress in the arts and by the post-war reor-
ganization of industry

e. as related to cost of production

12.30 p.m. to 2.00 p.m. Luncheon

2.00 p.m. to 4.30 p.m.

Continuation of Discussion either in main forum or in group con-
ferences to be arranged under leaders.

Third Day WEDNESDAY September 11, 1929

10.00 a.m. to 12.30 p.m.

Topic: Financial statements

I. Principles of Valuation:

a. Capital assets

Historical Versus present day costs including post war reva-
luations and exchange and currency problems.

b. Current assets

Inventory control including valuation of basic stocks at normal
prices.

Discussion.

II. Standardization of Balance Sheets

Consolidated balance sheets.

Problem of Earned Surplus in case of no-par value stock and
the availability of that surplus for dividends.

Discussion:

12.30 p.m. to 2.00 p.m. Luncheon

2.00 p.m. to 4.30 p.m.

III. Public Accountants' Certificates

Form and test

Accountants Reports, both public and private, i.e. form, test and
content. Presentation of statistical material.

Discussion:

IV. The Accountant's responsibility for the Inventory.

Discussion.

Fourth Day THURSDAY September 12, 1929

10.30 a.m. to 12.30 p.m.

Topic: Costs of Production

Standard Costs — predetermined

Procedures — operative procedures

Discussion:

Note: This session would afford an excellent opportunity for the
foreign visitors to discuss the progress of cost accounting in their
own countries.

12.30 p.m. to 2.00 p.m. Luncheon

2.00 p.m. to 4.30 p.m.

Topic: Selling Costs

Possibly continue the work of Mr. Bullis who is making a survey
on this subject for the N.A.C.A.

Discussion

Fifth Day FRIDAY September 13, 1929

10.00 a.m. to 12.30 p.m.

Topic: Commercial Budgetary Practice
 1. Present Status
 2. Forecasting and planning
 3. Financial control policies in industry

Discussion:

12.30 p.m. 2.00 p.m. Luncheon

Possibly devoted to an address on International and National status of Commercial Arbitration. The American association of Arbitration would probably be willing to provide a speaker (Charles Evans Hughes suggested).

2.00 p.m. to 4.30 p.m.

Topic: Municipal and Governmental Budgets.
 1. Income and Expenditure basis
 2. Uniformity of reporting
 a. ordinary and extraordinary revenues and expenses
 b. Uniformity of reporting
 3. Municipal Balance Sheets and budget practice

Discussion

Sixth Day SATURDAY September 14, 1929

Business Session:

Skeleton organization in anticipation of next Congress.
 Voting on non-binding resolutions to be submitted by the delegates on matters of practice, procedure and policy growing out of the discussions of the Congress. It is felt that here will be afforded in excellent opportunity for the Congress to record its conclusions on important topics.

Discussion on

- a. An international periodical for accountants
- b. Foundation of an International Chamber of Accountants
- c. The adoption of the National business year
- d. The adoption of the thirteen month year (calendar reform) Eastman plan. Possibly the Eastman Company will supply literature in several languages or otherwise in this matter.

VRAGENBUS

Vragen omtrent onderwerpen, die voor den accountant in de uitoefening van zijn beroep van belang kunnen zijn, kunnen worden ingezonden bij den Secretaris van de Redactie.

De Redactie is bereid, om de grenzen, waarbinnen de vragen, die voor beantwoording in aanmerking komen, zoo ruim mogelijk te stellen, zoodat zoowel die van juridischen, als die van bedrijfshuishoudkundigen aard daar binnen vallen, mits de vragen slechts blijven binnen het gebied, dat het blad dienen wil.

De beantwoording geschiedt door één der medewerkers of redactieleden individueel, zoodat de antwoorden niet mogen worden geacht steeds de meening der Redactie in haar geheel weer te geven.

REPERTORIUM VAN TIJDSCHRIFT-LITERATUUR OP HET GEBIED VAN ACCOUNTANCY EN BEDRIJFSHUISHOUDKUNDE

Redactie: Mej. Dr. R. PHILIPS en Drs. G. L. GROENEVELD voor bedrijfseconomie en J. P. DE HAAN en J. C. SPANGENBERG voor accountancy

(De Systematiek, welke in dit repertorium wordt gevolgd, is uiteengezet in het nummer van Januari 1929 van dit blad)

A. ACCOUNTANCY

III. LEER VAN DE INRICHTING

Besteldienst G.E.B. Den Haag.

Benoist, G. J. J. — Schr. bespreekt de formulieren, bij dezen dienst in gebruik.
 A III 3 (A 35) *De Gemeentefinanciën van 5 Jan. 1929.*

Magazijnbeheer en magazijnadministratie

Donk, A. van — Schr. geeft de magazijnboekhouding, die bij de gemeente Steenwijk zal worden ingevoerd.
 A III 3 (A 23) *De Gemeentefinanciën van 19 Jan. 1929.*

Beschrijving van de administratie van de afdeling „kapitaalverzekering” van de N.V. „Noord-Brabant” Maatschappij van verzekering op het leven te Waalwijk I

Huijsmans, H. — De boeking der tot stand gekomen verzekeringen met behulp van Elliot-Fisher en Visiblex Kaartstelsel.
 A III 3 (A 35) *Administratieve Arbeid van Jan. 1929.*

Municipal accounts exemplified

Whitehead, S. — Geeft enkele wenken voor de samenstelling van de jaarlijksche rekening.
 A III 3 (A 23) *The Accountants' Journal van Jan. 1929.*

Dupliceremachines

Vonk, W. — De voordeelen van alsmede de sorteering in dupliceremachines worden besproken.
 A III 3 (A 35) *Administratieve Arbeid van Jan. 1929.*

IV. LEER VAN DE CONTROLE

Requirements of a balance sheet audit

Couchman, Ch. B. — Bespreekt de onvolledigheid van het balansonderzoek. De accountant moet veelal afgaan op „confirmations” zoowel van derden als van geïnteresseerden. De behandeling van de rekeningen „Accounts Receivable” en „Inventory” worden speciaal behandeld.
 A IV 2 (A 33) *The Journal of Accountancy van Jan. 1929*

Accountants' certificates

Fernald, H. B. — Bezieet de accountantsverklaringen voornamelijk uit het oogpunt van credietonderzoeken. Bespreekt de betrekkelijke waarde, welke de door den accountant bij zijn onderzoek vergaarde kennis heeft. De Engelsche verklaring is z.i. de beste. Overeenstemming met betrekking tot de beteekenis van de accountantsverklaring moet verkregen worden tusschen bankiers, credietnemers, het publiek in het algemeen en de accountants.
 A IV 2 (A 33) *The Journal of Accountancy van Jan. 1929.*

Standard Financial-Statement Form for Banks.

Saxe, E. — Geeft een standaardvragenformulier te gebruiken bij credietonderzoeken door banken.
 A IV 3 (B 6a) *The Journal of Accountancy van Jan. 1929.*

B. BEDRIJFSHUISHOUDKUNDE

II. BEDRIJFSHUISHOUDKUNDE ALS WETENSCHAP

De ontwikkeling van de bedrijfsleer als toegepaste wetenschap

Goudriaan, Prof. Dr. Ir. J. — De bezwaren van practici en theoretici worden ontzenuwd. Schr. geeft vervolgens een indeeling der bedrijfsleer volgens de functies in het bedrijf. De algemeene kenmerken der bedrijfsleerlitteratuur worden geteekend, en de belangrijkheid van bewerking van grondmateriaal en een zeker karaktervormend element bij het onderwijs in de bedrijfsleer worden naar voren gebracht.
 B a II 1 (A 1) *De Ingenieur 1928 (p. T. 77—T 86)*